

The Impact of Dispositional Traits and Job Satisfaction on Employee Turnover Intentions

Author Detail: Dr. Niamatullah Shah

Abstract

Individuals are the most important factor in the organization on which employers and managers rely to face the complex issues and make critical decisions. Accordingly, organizations invest a lot on hiring, training and for furnishing their employees with skills and expertise, to use all of them for their own benefits. However, when employees leave the organizations, hurt their interest and all the investment goes to waste. This research study investigated the relationships between dispositional traits and job satisfaction to employee turnover intention. By applying Multiple Regression Analysis on 134 sample of private banking sector, this study concluded that positive affectivity and job satisfaction has negatively significant relationship with turnover intention. However, negative affectivity has now relationship with turnover intention. This research may contribute to the literature of organizational and individual development. Furthermore it may help human resource experts to understand turnover intentions more precisely then before and assist in making new human resource policies and strategies.

Keywords: turnover intention, dispositional traits, positive affectivity, negative affectivity, job, job satisfaction.

Introduction

Turnover intention has been one of the most complicated areas of research for human resource (HR) experts. Employee when leave the organization, puts the investments in vague, results in loss of assets as money, training, experience and time for hiring a new one. Turnover is voluntary or involuntary withdrawal from an organization while turnover intention is the predictor of this act (Tett and Meyer, 1993). Both, voluntary and involuntary turnover cost a lot to organization (Cascio, 1991). Involuntary turnover is organizational decision to leave an employee which impacts the morale of remaining staff, reduces their job security, and loss of expertise as well. Voluntary turnover is employees own act of leaving. Employees quit when better career opportunities, increased pay, high fringe benefits, more procedural and distributive justice and so many other factors attract the employees towards external market (Wright, 1993).

Researchers and human resources practitioners are continuously trying to investigate the factors leading to turnover intentions. Number of variables such as job satisfaction, organizational commitment, age, tenure, kinship responsibilities, education, experience, rate of employment, job availabilities, and personality affects has been observed in this connection. However, the relationship of turnover intention and dispositional traits is quite complex, requires deep scholarly inquiry. Indeed disposition is psychological characteristic of behavior as needs, motives, attitude, preferences, personality and particular style to respond any situation, different in state of temperament, activation and usefulness. Disposition is the most permanent factor that can be defined in two distinct dimensions i.e. positive affects and negative affects. Both are personality

predictors and highly contribute to understand one's attitude and response in any specific situation.

Reviewing previous research, it was found that large amount of research have been conducted in the area of turnover intention (Cascio, 1991; Aaron, 1999; Shaw et al., 2000; Peerbhai, 2006; Minor et al., 2009; Ahmed and Riaz, 2011; Wadhwa, 2011). However, there is still need to examine the more factors with different correlation and context. Researchers like Rahman (2008) investigated the relationship of job satisfaction, organizational commitment and perceived alternative job opportunities to employee turnover intention. To date less research has been found in the literature with the relationship of dispositional traits and job satisfaction with employee turnover intention. Filling to this gap void, this research has proposed to examine the relationship of dispositional traits, job satisfaction and turnover intentions. This research may contribute to the literature of organizational development and organizational management in general and in particular it may increase the understanding of turnover intention in Asian organizational context.

Literature Review and Conceptual Framework

Turnover intention is the desire of employee to leave an organization voluntarily (Nazim, 2008). Turnover inflicts severe harm to organization both financially and psychologically. Financially it cost the loss of money invested on employees while psychologically it effects the morale and job satisfaction of other workers left behind. Organizations invest a lot on hiring, training and for furnishing their employees with skills and expertise, to use all of them for their own benefits. Employees when leave the organizations, hurt

their interest and all the investment goes to waste. It creates more complications when the same talent and skills are occupied and used by the market competitors. In this situation it has become essential for employers to keep hold their workers in hand, making them not to leave organization unnecessarily. Turnover intention has emerged as one of the most complicated human resources areas for researchers and scholars, because of its importance and impacts on the organizations. Researchers condemned this act as occupational crime (Ahmed and Riaz, 2011). Empirical research on turnover intention discovered a number of organizational, personal, work related and environmental factors responsible for this behavior. According to Judge (1993) that affective disposition moderates between job satisfaction and turnover. Results from 234 medical clinic workers revealed that individuals endorsed more satisfaction with the items on the gripe index were more probable to leave an unfavorable job. In another study Duffy, Ganster, and Shaw (1998) surveyed a sample of 191 fire and police department employees and found that among the employees with high tenure, those highest in job search were high on trait positive affectivity. Beside these same employees possessed low job satisfaction. On the other hand, employees with low tenures demonstrate high job satisfaction and low positive affectivity. A three-way interaction was found between job satisfaction, positive affectivity, and tenure on job search behaviors. Their results showed that for high tenured individuals, positive affectivity had a much stronger moderator effect on job satisfaction and job search (i.e. high positive affectivity employees searched for a new job more in an unsatisfying situation than low positive affectivity employees).

For low tenure individuals, the exact reverse relationship was observed. Ahmed and Riaz, (2011) reported a study to investigate the factors effecting turnover intentions. Researcher used non probability method of convenient sampling. From the data of 231 samples results showed that multiple variables (job satisfaction, perceived job alternatives, distributive justice, work load and management style) were responsible for turnover intentions and their combination was found significant in turnover intentions.

By reviewing the literature, it was found that researchers paid a good deal of interest to the area of turnover intention. Researchers used multiple variables include various work and non-work related factors such as age, gender, tenure, kinship responsibilities, city size, rate of unemployment, lack of job availability, cost of turnover, position in the firm, task repetitiveness, fringe benefits, organizational commitment and job satisfaction (Cohen, 1993; Aaron, 1999; Chiu and Francesco, 2003; Peerbhai, 2006; Ahmed and Riaz, 2011). Most prominent factor among them was job satisfaction. Literature supports the significance of job satisfaction in the prediction of turnover intention as well as their role as mediator between dispositional traits and turnover intentions. Moreover researchers suggested extending the model of dispositional traits and turnover intentions introducing more work related outcomes (Chiu and Francesco, 2003). It is also argued by researchers that very few studies have been conducted examining the turnover intention in Asian organizational context that considered few variables. Based on research gap, this study proposes to examine the impact of dispositional traits and job satisfaction to turnover intention.

Fig: 1 Proposed conceptual model of research

Hypotheses Development

Human tendencies to respond in same style over time are referred as dispositional affects. These affects are conceptually related with personality traits. Positive affects are related with high energy, enthusiasm, and pleasant attitude. Conversely negative affects are characterized with distress, nervousness and aggressiveness (Watson et al, 1988). Both positive affectivity and negative affectivity are independent that predict attitude and behavior. positive affectivity reflects pervasive individual emotionality of positive feelings that reflects person's predisposition of being happy. negative affectivity defines person's negative emotions as disappointment, threat and shortcomings (Watson and Clark, 1984). Considerable researches found significant relationship between dispositional traits and turnover intention (Judge, 1993; Duffy et al., 1998; Chiu and Francesco, 2003; Mazzola, 2006). Chiu and Francesco (2003) found that positive affectivity is inversely associated with turnover intentions while negative affectivity positively impact on employee's turnover intention. Moreover researcher argued that role of job satisfaction and affective commitment is mediating between these variables. Against these findings, Mazzola (2006) investigated that dispositional traits have no say in turnover intention. Researcher found justice and job satisfaction effective on turnover intention. Reviewing literature it is observed that there is enough contradiction in the results of previous research studies. It is found valuable to test same variables in present research for further investigations. Hence it is hypothesized that;

H1. Positive affectivity is positively and significantly related to turnover intention.

H2. Positive affectivity is positively and significantly related to turnover intention.

Many previous researches confirm the negative relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intentions. Korunka et al. (2005) investigated the link between organizational professional conflicts, job satisfaction and turnover intentions and explored the negative relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intentions. Lambert, Hogan and Barton (2001) verified job satisfaction strongly negatively related with turnover intentions. Chiu and Francesco (2003) examined the mediatory effects of job satisfaction in the relationship of dispositional traits and turnover intention. Researcher found that job satisfaction has significant relationship with positive affectivity and negatively affect turnover intention. Going through literature review it is observed that no other research has been found in Asian Culture organization. Present research is going to further investigate the relationship between job satisfaction and employees turnover intention in the continuation of previous research findings.

H2: Employees job satisfaction is positively and significantly related to turnover intention.

Research methodology

Following previous renowned researchers this research is proposed as a cross sectional study where deductive approach is proposed for this study. In organizational behavior literature many renowned researchers like Lambert et al. (2001); Chiu and Francesco (2003); Rahman (2008), applied this approach and used quantitative methods for getting objects. Following to domain researcher, the study has been applied quantitative approach to collect data. In this regard a survey questionnaire has been adapted from the literature for collection of data.

Population, Sample and Procedure for distribution

The researcher proposes population of private banking sector in Hyderabad district. Total population in private banking sector of the district is more than 1000. From this population, researcher randomly selected 200 sample sizes and required return sample is 67%. The researcher distributed a packets of survey consist on questionnaires, letter from supervisor, covering letter mentioning the purpose of the study, and instructions on how to complete the survey instrument. Before distributing survey, the researcher obtained consent from participants for volunteer participation. The survey instrument has been handed over by personal visit, through mail and email service. Before distributing the questionnaire; participants were contacted to determine their willingness to take part in the study. Participation was volunteer basis and it informed that at any time participant can withdraw. The survey instrument was administered in English.

Measurements Scales

Turnover intention: The researcher used four-item scale adapted from Kelloway, Gottlieb and Barham (1999) to measure turnover intentions as a dependent variable. All items will be measured on 5-point Likert scale

Job satisfaction: Researcher used a shortened version of five items from Spector’s (1997) Job Satisfaction Survey as used by Harman et al. (2009). Items were measured with a Likert-type, 5-point scale.

Dispositional traits: Positive and negative affectivity were measured through positive and negative affect schedule (PANAS) of Watson, Clark, and Tellegen, (1988) as used by Crawford et al.(2004) on rated five point Likert scale

Data Analysis

Data was recorded and coded in Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20.0 for Windows. After cleaning the data, reliability and validity test was tested. A descriptive statistics test including mean and standard deviation was conducted to describe the demographic results. After that factor loading was conducted by applying a principal component analysis techniques to determine the factors of relevant variables. All factors were loaded to their respective items and found empirically different from each other and conceptually validated. The researcher applied Cronbach’s coefficient alpha test to measure the reliability of survey questionnaire. However, the survey questionnaire validity was measured through field experts (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). For testing hypotheses, the researcher conducted Pearson’s Correlation test and Multiple Regression Analysis technique was applied.

Results

Reliability, Descriptive statistics and Pearson’s correlations

The researcher applied Cronbach’s Alpha for measuring reliability of survey questionnaire. Individual factor reliability of factors such as turnover intention, dispositional traits and job satisfaction has been found .90 .78, .82 respectively (see Table 1). However, overall reliability was found .89. Statistical results of descriptive statistics showed that overall participants turnover intention was low and job satisfaction was high. From the Pearson’s correlation test it was found that personality traits were positive and significant relationship with employee turnover intention. However, the relationship of job satisfaction with turnover intention was negative and significant relationships. In this test significant correlations between the scales were determined at two levels (p=0.05 and p=0.01). However from demographic variables such that age, gender and marital status was not found significant turn over intention (see Table1).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics, reliability and Pearson correlations (N=134)

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7.
1 Age	---	---	1						
2 Gender	---	---	.145	1					
3 Marital Status	---	---	.512	.142	1				
4 Positive Affectivity	0.63	0.51	.372**	.251	.321	1			
5 Negative Affectivity	0.43	0.63	.511	.162	.216	.316	1		
6 Job Satisfaction	3.74	0.82	.351**	.241*	.532**	.471**	.512	1	
7 Turnover Intention	2.01	0.95	.151	.312	.517	-.231*	.221	-.562**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Note: M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

Testing Hypotheses

In this study hypotheses were tested by applying multiple regression analysis in which beta (β) value was used. H1 require a significant relationship between positive affectivity and turnover intention. Results showed that positive affectivity was negatively related to turnover intention (r = -.231 p < 0.05; and β = -.265 p < 0.05). Therefore, H1 was rejected. However, H2 states that NA is positively significant to turnover intention. Results showed that negative affectivity was not correlated to turnover intention (r = .221, NS; and β = .026, NS). Therefore, H2 was rejected. Results of regression test showed that the job satisfaction had no impact on employees turnover intention (r = -.562, p < 0.01; and β = -.436, p < 0.01) hence, H3 was also rejected.

Table 2. Multiple Regression

Variables	Model 1	Model 2
	B	B
Step 1: Control variables		
Gender	.215	
Age	-.061	
Marital status	.035	
Step 2: Main effects		
Positive Affectivity		-.265*
Negative Affectivity		.026
Job Satisfaction		-.436**
F value	.267	21.245
R ²	.052	.341
Adjusted R ²	-.028	.264
Change in adjusted R ²	.021	.371

Note: p* < 0.10; p** < 0.05

Discussions and Conclusions

The main purpose of this research work is to enhance our knowledge for understanding the factors that support to individual's turnover intention. This study was conducted in private banking sector of a developing country which may also support to understanding a particular mind set of employees of a country. In this study, the researchers investigate that how positive affectivity, negative affectivity, and job satisfaction directly influence turnover intention. The inferential results support to previous literature and generally all finding are matching with the studies conducted in West. Quantitative information collected from bank employees reported that positive affectivity and job satisfaction is negative significant related to employees turnover intention. However, negative affectivity has no relationship with turnover intention. These results support to the literature in general and particular in the context of a developing country.

Turnover is well known voluntary or involuntary withdrawal from an organization and predictor of this withdrawal related with turnover intention. According to Nazim (2008) that turnover intention is the desire of employee to leave an organization voluntarily. It can increase due to the frustration of employees which they face by day-to-day tasks. However, positive affectivity individuals have a propensity to handle easily with this type of frustration because they usually consider the bright side of any situation. Negative affectivity has opposite relationship than to positive affectivity. Happy workers with high positive affectivity have been found significantly

productive for organizations (Ahmed and Riaz, 2011). George and Brief (1996) ensured that happy workers are more productive for organization. Besides motivational perspective positive affect is a predictor of enhanced citizenship behavior as cooperation and helping others (George and Brief, 1992). Apart of that in unfavourable conditions, individuals with positive dispositions tend to consolidate their efforts very quickly to face future challenges. Thus, results of our research in general reported negative and significant to turnover intention. Literature also support that in the organisation, must create high positive affectivity for reducing turnover intention (Oldham and Fried, 1987). To the extent of these results, employers and management should create high positive affectivity in the organisation and this is the implications for organisations in a developing country.

Employees' job satisfaction is important to reduce the organisational financial and psychological loss. Given the condition a positive orientation to life has significant impact in predicting job satisfaction and, in turn, is unlikely to turn into turnover behaviour. This study also investigates the impact of employees' job satisfaction to turnover intention. Results of this research also support previous literature and generally all finding are matching with the studies conducted in West. Quantitative results reveals that job satisfaction is negative significant related to employees turnover intention. Similar results were found in the literature and suggest that employees job satisfaction is more important in reducing turnover.

In human resources practices, more specifically, turnover is considered severe harm to organization in the context of both financial and psychological. Financially it cost the loss of money invested on employees while psychologically it effects the morale and job satisfaction of other workers left behind. Thus, turnover intention has emerged as one of the most complicated human resources areas for researchers and scholars, because of its importance and impacts on the organizations. Researchers condemned this act as occupational crime (Ahmed and Riaz, 2011). Thus, at one level employers and managers should consider the use of selection methods that include testing for positive affectivity. To this extent researchers have suggested number of techniques through which management can induce positive affectivity. For example improving the physical environment, introducing an organisational culture that fosters a positive attitude towards employees, and enhancing organisational communication to raise the general level of positive affectivity among employees (Isen and Baron, 1991). From these results we suggest that not only inducing positive affectivity, but also enhancing the overall level of human resource management in developing countries.

This study consisted many theoretical and practical implications. In the literature, positive affectivity and job satisfaction support to reduce the employees turn over intention. Empirical evidence from this research support to the notion and provide guideline to the employers and managers to induce positive affectivity among employees. In addition, results suggest to provide facilities and all other support to increase job satisfaction in a developing country should discover how to manage turnover intention effectively in order to get organisational goals.

From the methodological point of view this research has also many limitations that needs to improve for future research. For example, this is a cross sectional study and all data were collected at same time. Given that condition, results of the study can be presumed but not confirm causality. Second limitation is of sample that data was collected from banking sector in a developing country. Therefore, these results may not be generalized to other organisations. Finally, the self reported data might be influenced by a social desirability response bias. Despite of these limitations, this research study provides deep insights into understanding the importance of

dispositional traits and job satisfaction to control over turnover intention in the developing culture. In conclusion, the empirical evidence support that positive affectivity and job satisfaction can reduce turnover intention in a developing country. The researchers proposed propose to investigate other factors that can reduce turn over intention with different sets in developing countries.

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